

Studies on 6,7-Benzomorphan Related Compounds—Synthesis of 5-Methyl-2-N-Phenethyl and 5-Methyl-2-N-Propyl-3, 4 : 6,7-Dibenzomorphan

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5-Methyl-2-N-phenethyl-3,4 : 6,7-dibenzomorphan (5) from 4-methyl-1-phenethylquinolinium iodide (1) and 5-methyl-2-N-propyl 3,4 : 6,7-dibenzomorphan (6) from 4-methyl-1-propyl quinolinium iodide (2) were synthesised based on Grewe's morphinan synthesis¹. The hydrochloride (3.HCl) of the intermediate (3) in the synthesis of (5) was identified as 2-benzyl-4-methyl-1-phenethylquinolinium chloride.

THE present communication deals with the synthesis of 5 and 6. The synthesis of 5 was an attempt to synthesise phenazocine analog (compound related to 6,7-benzomorphan)² to see the possibility of cyclization of benzyl group at position 4 of the quinoline ring having phenethyl group at position 1 resulting in the formation of the desired 3,4 : 6,7-dibenzomorphan. The success of the synthesis of 5 has opened the possibilities of synthesising

better substitutes related to 6,7-benzomorphan.

4-Methyl-1-phenethylquinolinium iodide 1 was synthesised² and reacted with benzyl magnesium chloride under Freund's reaction condition³. The unstable dihydro product 3 (presumably formed)⁴ was distilled under reduced pressure and was immediately kept for cyclization with 85% H₃PO₄. A small portion of it converted to its hydrochloride 3.HCl with ether-HCl was identified as 2-benzyl-4-methyl-1-phenethylquinolinium chloride. It has also been reported earlier that 2-benzyl-1,4-dimethyl-1,2-dihydroquinoline rearranged to 2-benzyl-1,4-dimethylquinolinium chloride and such rearrangements⁴ were also observed by Tilak and Subbaswami⁵. The ether soluble portion of the reaction product obtained after cyclisation of 3 was converted to its hydrochloride which was further basified to give 5. The purity of 5 was ascertained through tlc by using Silica Gel-G as absorbent and MeOH and CCl₄ (6 : 4) as mobile phase.

5-Methyl-2-N-propyl-3,4 : 6,7-dibenzomorphan 6 was synthesised starting from 4-methyl-1-propyl-

quinolinium iodide 2 on similar lines as followed in earlier cases⁴ and also in the synthesis of 5. 6 was synthesised to find whether the substitution of a propyl group in place of a methyl group at nitrogen would result in the improvement of pharmacological properties. However, 6 was found to be ineffective.

Structural Elucidation

4-Methyl-1-phenethylquinolinium iodide 1

The nmr spectrum of 1 (C₁₅H₁₈NI in T.F.A.) indicated the presence of eleven aromatic protons in the range of δ 6.3–8.25, of three protons for C-CH₃ group as singlet at δ 2.60, of two protons as triplet at δ 3.0 and another triplet for two protons at δ 4.82. On the basis of these observations the structure of 1 was assigned as 4-methyl-1-phenethylquinolinium iodide.

2-Benzyl-4-methyl-1-phenethylquinolinium chloride 3.HCl

The nmr spectrum of 3.HCl (C₂₅H₂₄NCl) in T.F.A. indicated the presence of a triplet for two protons at δ 3.05, another triplet for two protons at δ 4.85, a singlet for three protons at δ 2.65 and a singlet for two protons at δ 4.25. There was an indication for the presence of fifteen aromatic protons in the range of δ 6.4–8.25. On the basis of these observations the structure to 3.HCl was assigned as 2-benzyl-4-methyl-1-phenethylquinolinium chloride.

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5-Methyl-2-N-phenethyl-3,4 : 6,7-dibenzomorphan 5

The nmr spectrum of 5 ($C_{25}H_{25}N$) as oily base was obtained in CCl_4 using TMS as internal reference standard. The spectrum indicated the presence of thirteen aromatic protons in the range δ 6.6–8.25. A singlet for three protons for a $C-CH_3$ group was observed at δ 1.38. In the range of δ 1.8–4.0, a complicated pattern was obtained and the integration indicated the presence of nine protons which would account for the presence of two protons at C_8 , one proton at C_1 , two protons at C_9 and four protons at nitrogen. The presence of the singlet for three protons at higher field (shifted from δ 2.6 in 1 to δ 1.38 in 5) indicated the fact that cyclization had occurred resulting in the formation of desired compound 5. On the basis of these observations structure to 5 was assigned as 5-methyl-2-N-phenethyl-3,4 : 6,7-dibenzomorphan.

5-Methyl-2-N-propyl-3,4 : 6,7-dibenzomorphan 6

1-Propyl-4-methylquinolinium iodide 2 was reacted on similar lines with benzyl magnesium chloride and the intermediate was isolated without carrying any structural elucidation (as it is well known that these dihydro compounds undergo rearrangement as also stated earlier) was subjected to cyclization with 85% H_3PO_4 . The cyclized base was distilled under reduced pressure to the compound 6. The nmr spectrum of 6 ($C_{20}H_{23}N$) as base was done in CCl_4 using TMS as internal reference standard. There was an indication of eight aromatic protons in the range of δ 6.5–8.5. There was a triplet for three protons at δ 0.68 and a singlet for three protons at δ 1.52. In the complicated pattern at δ 1.8–2.43, there was an indication of nine protons. Thus the nmr spectrum has accounted well for the presence of

of benzyl group at position 5. The triplet for three protons at δ 0.68 was due to the methyl group of N-propyl moiety, the four protons of which might be in the range of δ 1.8–4.3, where the presence of five more protons must be due to two protons at C_8 , two protons at C_9 and one proton at C_1 . Based on these observations, the structure to 6 was assigned as 5-methyl-2-N-propyl-3,4 : 6,7-dibenzomorphan.

Experimental4-Methyl-1-phenethylquinolinium iodide 1

A solution of phenethyl iodide (6.96 g., 0.03M) in acetone (10 ml) was added over a period of 0.5 hr to 4-methylquinoline (4.29 g., 0.03M) in 10 ml of a mixture of acetone and benzene (5 : 5)². The mixture after having been refluxed for 10hr, deposited a yellow coloured solid on cooling. The solid was filtered and crystallised with acetone-benzene in light yellow needles (8.50 g, 75.5%, m.p. 142°).

5-Methyl-2-N-phenethyl-3,4 : 6,7-dibenzomorphan 5

To a suspension of 4-methyl-1-phenethylquinolinium iodide 1 (7.50 g, 0.02M) in absolute dry ether, benzyl magnesium chloride (Benzyl chloride 3.7950 g, 0.03M; magnesium 0.72 g, 0.03M; ether 50 ml) was added within 15 min. The reaction mixture was stirred continuously for 1 hr. at 10°–15° and for another 5 hr at 30°–35°. The reaction mixture was treated in the usual manner, and was distilled under reduced pressure when an oily substance was obtained (Yield 3.0 g, ca. 47.4%). As the dihydro compounds are unstable, only a small portion of it was converted to its hydrochloride 3.HCl for identification (m.p. 107°–10°) and the rest of the oily compound (2.50 g, 0.007M) was subjected to cyclization with 85% H_3PO_4 at 130°–40° for 72 hr. The reaction mixture was treated in usual manner. The ether soluble

twenty three protons in 6. The singlet at δ 1.52 for three protons indicated the presence of a methyl group at position 5 thus, establishing the cyclization

part of the crude product thus obtained was converted to its hydrochloride which on further basification gave the desired compound 5 as an oily liquid

(Yield 1.20 g, ca. 50%). A small amount of it was converted to its hydrochloride salt (m.p. 118°).

5-Methyl-2-N-propyl-3,4 : 6,7-dibenzomorphan 6

On similar lines as followed in the synthesis of 5, 4-methyl-1-propylquinolinium iodide 2 (6.26 g., 0.02M) was reacted with benzyl magnesium chloride (Benzyl chloride 3.7950 g, 0.03M; magnesium 0.72 g, 0.03M; ether 50 ml) and the dihydro compound (2.30 g, Ca. 41.7%) was obtained. This oily compound was cyclised in H₃PO₄ for 72 hr. The crude base thus obtained was distilled under reduced pressure and was crystallised with acetone to give a crystalline compound 5 (Yield 0.950 g, ca. 42.0%, m.p. 125°).

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